

Bridging Communities and Archives

Preserving digital Documents with the Citizen Archive Platform

The **Citizen Archive Platform** is a web-based tool that facilitates the structured transfer of born-digital data from individuals, communities and cultural initiatives to archives for long-term storage. The goal is to simplify and standardise the submission process.

Technical details

- CMS Word Press
- SQL Database
- Specialised Plugin for data processing

Data processing

- Upload-interface
- Automatic format validation and virus scan
- Technical metadata extraction

Submission Information Package
with files + all technical and content metadata

Metadata form

Good to know

- Standards-compliant (OAIS, METS, EAD)
- Technical and content metadata are combined in one XML
- Legal issues (copyright, blocking time and contract) are clarified during the submission process
- Open source: Other archives can use the platform; Publication via GitHub at the end of 2025

